

Forecast-driven and simulation-based decision support for weather-sensitive project scheduling

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Abstract – Many supply chain processes involve weather-sensitive outdoor activities, e.g., transportation or construction. However, research in forecast-driven methods that not only provide alerts but also offer dynamic decision support and automatic rescheduling at the level of individual tasks is still limited. Based on the case of modular healthcare construction, we develop a forecast-driven planning support tool that integrates real-time weather forecasts and historical climate data into project scheduling. The tool automatically evaluates each task’s feasibility against weather constraints. In its current state, it provides continuous monitoring of weather conditions and issues alerts when weather thresholds are likely to be exceeded. Current development focuses on the automated replanning capabilities and simulation-based scenario evaluation. The implementation uses an object-oriented Python framework and open-source weather APIs. To outline the potential of the method, we demonstrate intermediate results using the case of a modular healthcare facility provider.

Keywords – Planning, scheduling, simulation, decision support, digital platform, modular construction, weather

I. INTRODUCTION

Many supply chain processes involve outdoor activities, such as transportation, loading, unloading, or storing of goods or equipment. Specifically, construction and large-scale assembly tasks involve heavy equipment and must be executed outdoors, where wind, precipitation, temperature, or storms directly affect safety, productivity, and costs [1]. Climate change is increasing both the frequency and intensity of disruptive events, further amplifying the need for weather-robust planning. At the same time, numerical weather prediction is continuously improving in accuracy and resolution [2, 3] and has recently benefited from the introduction of machine learning [4]. Integrating reliable weather forecasting into project management can reduce delays and mitigate risks.

Modular construction, which is characterized by building components off-site in factory environments rather than on-site, has the potential to offer improved quality and efficiency [5]. Modular healthcare facilities (MHCFs) are medical buildings that are assembled from prefabricated modules, which are built off-site in a controlled factory environment and then transported and assembled on-site. The

modular approach allows for faster construction, scalability, and adaptability compared to traditional building methods. Modular healthcare facilities have raised attention of research and practice during the COVID-19 pandemic [6] and have the potential to tackle pressing issues regarding existing healthcare infrastructure [7].

However, the effectiveness of these solutions heavily relies on the efficient and reliable installation of the modular units, which remains a complex challenge. Delivering a MHCF requires coordinating modules that originate from multiple, geographically dispersed sites: storing and retrieving each module, transporting them via heavy-duty haulage, rigging on-site cranes and preparing the foundation, assembling the modules, linking the completed facility to utility networks, and commissioning. Each activity requires certain resources (personnel, equipment), is conducted at a specific location, must follow precedence constraints, and is possibly characterized by weather limits regarding multiple weather variables.

The project planners challenge is to devise a feasible schedule. A task schedule, however, once established, must be continuously monitored and adapted in response to dynamic circumstances. In this use-case, one of the most critical and disruptive factors affecting schedule feasibility is weather. Thus, the feasibility of a project schedule must be continuously reassessed as updated weather forecasts become available. If predicted weather conditions violate the constraints of upcoming tasks, the schedule may have to be adjusted accordingly. Effective planning tools must therefore not only support the creation of an initial feasible schedule, but also support ongoing evaluation and adaptation in response to evolving weather conditions.

Recent research addresses this integration of weather information to enhance the planning of logistics processes. For example, Atencio *et al.* [8] have integrated weather information into building information modeling to generate alerts in the case of hazardous weather conditions. Ballesteros-Pérez *et al.* [9] introduced a planning tool that analyzes historical weather data for a given location and project to identify the optimal window to begin work. Rey *et al.* [10] have developed a web-based project management tool that integrates information from weather forecasts. Furthermore, weather influences on project scheduling have been of considerable interest for both the onshore [11] and offshore [12, 13] wind turbine installation context. A recent systematic literature review identifies a multitude of approaches aimed at performance improvement of construction scheduling that are often focusing on deducing

schedule improvements from long-term statistical analysis based on historical data [14]. However, research in forecast-driven tools that not only provide alerts but also offer dynamic decision support and automatic rescheduling at the level of individual tasks is still limited (cf. [9]).

In this context, we are developing a decision support tool for planning under weather uncertainty that will enable automated short-term project rescheduling assistance. The system integrates project schedules with location-specific weather forecasts, provides real-time monitoring and alerts, and will be extended to autonomously generate and evaluate alternative scheduling scenarios. In this paper, we present the concept and current state of development of the method, which is developed as part of the RaRe2 project. The RaRe2 project aims to develop a holistic ecosystem platform designed to enhance the adaptability and resilience of European manufacturing [15, 16]. The platform enables early detection of disruptions and supports decision-making through real-time alerts, and rapidly simulates alternative scenarios for fast reconfiguration of supply and process chains in response to changing conditions. The developed method assists the project planner as early as during schedule creation and enables continuous monitoring.

In the following, Section II details the design-science research methodology used, Section III describes the modular-healthcare use-case process, Section IV presents the current state of the forecast-driven decision-support tool and its implementation, and Section V concludes with key findings and future work.

II. METHODOLOGY

The design of the method follows the design science research methodology process model [17], which consists of six phases. The problem-centered initiation started from prior research of the authors and insights from initial workshops with the industry and research partners of RaRe2.

To (1) *identify the problem*, we conducted several daily workshops with the industry partner and used the Business Process Model and Notation (BPMN) method to capture the entire process from customer order to delivery of the modules.

Following that, to (2) *define the objectives of a solution*, we first identified areas of opportunity in the mapped order fulfilment process and then developed and iteratively refined user stories that describe the identified solution approaches from the user’s perspective.

To (3) *design and develop* the method, we use the object-oriented paradigm and the Python programming language as well as open-source data providers with a focus on modularity, extensibility, and unrestricted availability. The method is being implemented in three phases: (i) user-requested monitoring of the weather-related project feasibility, (ii) alerting system via automatic observation of task feasibility, and (iii) automated rescheduling and evaluation of alternative schedule scenarios.

The (4) *demonstration* of the developed method is carried out based on exemplary real-world projects of the use

case partner to retrieve feedback from both the potential end users and the development partners of the RaRe2 platform. Furthermore, a simulation model is being developed to evaluate the developed forecasting and scheduling methods.

To (5) *evaluate* the proposed method, it is quantitatively assessed using various performance metrics, including the number of prevented weather limit violations and overall schedule duration (cf. [11]), based on historical scenarios provided by the use case partners and corresponding weather data. To confirm the scalability among related industries, related use cases are identified and considered during the evaluation phase. Additionally, interoperability with other components of the RaRe2 platform is evaluated iteratively throughout the integration process.

III. USE CASE PROCESS DESCRIPTION

Our use case partner is both the manufacturer and service provider for the planning and implementation of MHCFs, designed for use in hospitals and life science facilities. Customers can lease or purchase a MHCF. Beyond manufacturing, the partner also manages installation and regulatory approvals, delivering each MHCF as a fully operational, ready-to-use solution.

The planning and implementation processes can be described as follows. For each project, i.e., an installation of a MHCF at a specific site, the service provider creates a detailed schedule containing all required tasks with start and end times: Just-in-time before the installation date, the modules are picked up from the storage site(s) and transported by truck to the installation site. Thereby, different required modules may be stored at different locations across Europe. After all units have been delivered, the modules are placed in position, assembled into a complete structure, connected to the utility infrastructure, and commissioned. The schedule also includes the involvement of subcontractors, e.g., logistics providers or crane subcontractors.

Crucially, several key activities are weather-sensitive: high winds halt crane lifts, rain may disrupt assembly or ground works, and snow or ice can close haulage routes. Because the provider contractually guarantees a hand-over date, yet lacks ad hoc buffer storage for the large modules and must adhere to transport permits, schedule flexibility is limited and any weather delay can cascade into a major schedule failure. The continuous monitoring of weather conditions before the installation date provides the service provider with an opportunity to increase planning reliability, and, if necessary, to coordinate changes to the plan in good time with the customer and the involved subcontractors.

This use-case thus highlights the need for a proactive planning tool that continuously monitors forecasts, flags weather risks, and enables rapid rescheduling which is described in the following section.

IV. DECISION SUPPORT TOOL

The decision support tool is implemented in Python using an object-oriented programming paradigm (Fig. 1). At the core of the system, lies the process plan class, which encapsulates the essential attributes and methods required to model, evaluate, and adapt task schedules in response to changing weather conditions. This design promotes modularity, reusability, and extensibility of the decision logic.

An instance of the process plan class is automatically constructed from three structured input datasets: a project specific task schedule, a set of weather conditions, and a set of weather constraints. Weather conditions are defined as atomic rules consisting of a weather variable (e.g., wind speed), a relational operator (e.g., $<$, $>$), and a threshold value. These conditions serve as building blocks for higher-level weather constraints, which may combine multiple weather conditions or other weather constraints using logical operators such as AND or OR to represent complex environmental limitations. An example for such weather constraint is that precipitation is allowed *if* temperatures exceed a certain limit. The task schedule includes the spatial and temporal attributes for each activity, such as planned start and end times, geographic coordinates, and also the associated weather constraints. During instantiation, the complete set of weather constraints is assembled from the input prior to task processing. Once the constraints have been constructed, each task is assigned its corresponding constraints by reference. The resulting process plan instance contains a structured representation of all tasks and their associated feasibility conditions, enabling systematic evaluation, alerting, and adaptive replanning within the decision support framework.

A central capability of the process plan class is the retrieval of weather forecasts and historical weather data based on the spatiotemporal information of its tasks. For this, the Open-Meteo API is used, which offers free access for non-commercial use and provides (ensemble) forecasts and historical weather data [18]. To retrieve the required weather data, the process plan object first analyzes all tasks and their associated constraints to determine the set of relevant weather variables and locations. This is done by resolving each constraint into its underlying weather condition objects, each of which specifies a weather variable and a threshold condition.

The weather data retrieval serves two major purposes: (1) to inform the decision maker during initial project planning about typical weather conditions at the relevant location and (2) to enable continuous monitoring, alerting, and automatic replanning on a tactical and operational level during project execution.

Projects are planned months ahead, and thus, a long-term weather forecast is required. Different methods to create long term forecasts exist. They have in common that they “cannot produce the details of future weather conditions on a day-to-day basis, but they can provide projected deviations from average conditions over the weeks and months ahead” [3].

Fig. 1: Simplified excerpt of the class diagram for the weather-based decision support tool

The current naive implementation is inspired by the Typical Meteorological Year [19] and is implemented to define data structures, logical flows and interfaces. With ongoing development of the method, different methods to generate more precise long-term forecasts will be evaluated. Currently, the Open-Meteo Historical Weather API [18] is used to retrieve historical weather data for the past 50 years. These historical records are grouped by day-of-year and hour, which provides an hourly “typical” weather profile for each weather variable and location.

For the continuous short-term monitoring and possible replanning of ongoing projects, a higher degree of forecast reliability is required. Somewhat relevant deterministic weather forecasts are available up until around 14 days [2]. Deterministic forecasts provide a single forecast, which can be compared against the given weather limits. In the current implementation, the process plan object queries the Open-Meteo Weather Forecast API [18] to retrieve short-term forecasts with hourly resolution for the upcoming 16 days. This is concatenated with the long-term forecast, giving a seamless, hourly time series that spans the entire planning horizon for every weather variable referenced by the project’s constraints.

The process plan object also holds the capability to conduct the task feasibility analysis. For each task, all associated weather constraints are evaluated at every forecast time step using a compositional logic. Individual weather conditions are checked against the forecast, and composite constraints are resolved via logical operators (AND/OR). The result is a time-indexed feasibility matrix indicating

task_ID	Task	Date																	
		2025-05-28	2025-05-29	2025-05-30	2025-05-31	2025-06-01	2025-06-02	2025-06-03	2025-06-04	2025-06-05	2025-06-06	2025-06-07	2025-06-08	2025-06-09	2025-06-10	2025-06-11	2025-06-12	2025-06-13	2025-06-14
22a	Storage site 1 – Prepare modules	Green																	
25a	Crane rigging	Green																	
26a	Load the modules	Green																	
30a	Transport modules to customer	Green																	
22c	Storage Site 2 – Prepare modules	Green																	
25c	Crane rigging	Green																	
26c	Load the modules	Green																	
30c	Transport modules to customer	Green																	
30d	Installation site - Site preparation	Green																	
33a	Crane rigging	Green																	
34a	Installation of modules	Green																	

Fig. 2: Example of deterministic feasibility analysis aggregated by day and task for weather critical tasks of an exemplary project schedule (green = feasible, red = non-feasible, current schedule = yellow striped)

whether each constraint – and in aggregate, each task – is feasible, infeasible, or indeterminate (i.e., when no forecast value is available) at a given time slot. To enable rapid assessment of overall conditions, this detailed feasibility matrix is aggregated across weather constraints to the task level and over time to daily and weekly levels, using the following priority logic: infeasibility overrides missing forecast data, which in turn overrides feasibility. This is then visualized for the planner. Fig. 2 shows a view aggregated over tasks and days, further indicating the planned project times (yellow striped) and the results of the feasibility analysis (green = feasible, red = non-feasible). The figure demonstrates the ability of the developed tool to visualize weather-induced risks well in advance. In the RaRe2 platform, the user will be able to zoom in to evaluate the feasibility in more detail regarding individual weather constraints and time resolution.

This deterministic evaluation will be extended to incorporate probabilistic reasoning. By leveraging, e.g., ensemble weather forecasts, each binary feasibility outcome can be complemented with an estimated probability of exceedance. An ensemble forecast comprises multiple individual forecasts of a certain weather variable for the same duration, generated by running weather prediction models with varying initial conditions or atmospheric representations. This accounts for the two main sources of forecast uncertainty [3]. This enables downstream decision-makers and algorithms to account for the natural uncertainty around the weather forecasts and optimize plans based on risk-aware criteria.

In the current implementation, the Open-Meteo Ensemble API [18] is used to retrieve ensemble forecasts for 35 days. This data is then used to compute the likelihood of exceedance by dividing the number of ensemble members that exceeded a specific weather constraint with the total number of ensemble members. More sophisticated approaches of the computation, e.g., via distribution fitting will be evaluated and can further improve this probabilistic analysis. Fig. 3 shows an exemplary visualization of the probabilistic analysis of a 35-day ensemble forecast for a specific location (in Germany) and weather condition (wind speed at 10 meters height) including the probability of exceedance (of 4 m/s).

Fig. 3: Exemplary visualization of probabilistic analysis of ensemble forecast of 35 days

The developed alert system is based on the ensemble forecasts probabilities of exceedance. The tool assesses the weather situation in regular intervals and computes the probabilities of exceedance for each task and constraint. Based on a user defined safety level, it identifies critical cases and is currently implemented to raise alerts (in JSON format) returning the project id, task id, weather constraint, probability of exceedance and related timeframe. The alerts will be provided to the RaRe2 platform, which will then visualize those in the overall project dashboard.

Having established a probabilistic weather-monitoring method that visualizes forecast risk and issues alerts when the baseline schedule is threatened, the final step in the development phase will be to enable automated replanning and its simulation-based validation. The core concept is to treat each forecast update as a stochastic information set, translate it into task-specific feasibility information, and then generate a candidate set of revised schedules that follow different objectives, e.g., a quickest or safest schedule. A broad spectrum of techniques can be deployed for this purpose (see, e.g., [11–13, 20]). Each candidate schedule will then be subjected to a stochastic simulation that simulates the execution of the schedule in a controlled environment. Stochastic components of the model will include, e.g., the weather, the processing times of the different tasks, the resource availability and uptime regarding cranes, trucks, operators, or the traffic. The simulation will measure the distribution of key performance indicators like project duration and idle-time costs over a multitude of replications. It will then summarize those with the help of statistical methods to provide confidence intervals of the performance of each evaluated schedule candidate. These summaries will be presented to the project planner to provide a solid data base for decision making.

The simulation model is currently developed as an agent-based simulation model. Besides the main agent that represents the simulation environment, further agents are modules, trucks for module transportation and cranes for loading, unloading and installation of the modules. For rapid prototyping, the agent-based discrete-event simulation is currently implemented in AnyLogic, whose visual modelling environment accelerates model construction and communication with domain experts. In the envisaged operational roll-out, this prototype implemented in an open-

source simulation framework (e.g., SimPy) to remove licensing constraints and ensure seamless integration with the optimization and data-analytics components already developed in Python.

V. CONCLUSION AND OUTLOOK

In this paper, we presented a prototype decision-support tool that integrates weather forecasts into project scheduling, enabling automatic feasibility checking and proactive alerts for weather-critical tasks. This approach can improve schedule reliability and safety in weather-sensitive projects. Preliminary application of the tool with a sample MHCf project schedule demonstrated its ability to flag weather-induced risks well in advance, validating the approach's practical value. Future work will focus on improving the applied forecasting methods, usability, and platform interoperability, as well as implementing automated rescheduling capabilities and scenario evaluation through simulation-based experiments. This research contributes to more resilient project scheduling under weather uncertainty and will continue to evolve as part of the broader RaRe2 decision-support platform.

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